

Implementation and evaluation of a tele-reha as well as a paper-based aftercare programme following inpatient rehabilitation: a three-armed, observer-blinded, randomised controlled trial

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Content

1	BACKGROUND	2
2	METHOD.....	3
2.1	Study Design	3
2.2	Intervention	4
2.2.1	Tele-Reha Group Intervention	4
2.2.2	Control Group Interventions.....	6
2.3	Sample Size	6
2.4	Participants.....	7
2.5	Randomisation	8
2.6	Blinding of assessors	9
2.7	Assessment	9
2.8	Quantitative Data Analysis	11
2.9	Ethical Considerations.....	12
2.10	Data Security.....	12
2.11	Adverse events/safety reports	12
2.12	Benefit/risk evaluation	12
3	REFERENCES	13

1 BACKGROUND

Rehabilitation reduces activity limitations and participation restrictions and enables functioning in daily life. Thus, rehabilitation improves a person's quality of life and focuses on symptom management, personal goals and preferences (Del Pino et al., 2022). For both acute and chronic conditions, early access to rehabilitation and long-term continuity of care is crucial for symptom recovery in many cases (Feigin et al., 2020).

In neurological conditions, multidisciplinary stroke rehabilitation has been shown to reduce the likelihood of institutionalisation and long-term disability and increases independence in activities of daily living (Kalra & Langhorne, 2007; Pollock et al., 2014). However, stroke survivors have expressed concerns about the lack of long-term support and the ongoing need for non-pharmacological rehabilitation (Ullberg et al., 2016) - a problem that most likely also exists for persons with other neurological diseases.

Following inpatient rehabilitation treatment, telerehabilitation can potentially ensure continuity of care at home, particularly for persons with chronic conditions, by supporting individuals to resume their life tasks following discharge (Laver et al., 2020). Telerehabilitation has been described as an alternative method to delivering traditional rehabilitation services, and interest in its use is growing as technologies become more widespread and advanced (Brochard et al., 2010; Galea, 2019). Since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, telerehabilitation has significantly contributed to treatment accessibility (Prvu Bettger & Resnik, 2020) and has become a valuable solution for patient care.

However, despite the reported benefits of telerehabilitation (Stinear et al., 2020), implementation in clinical practice is slow (Standing et al., 2018) and has not yet reached standard care. To address this gap in continuing care after discharge from an inpatient facility through telerehabilitation, our project has the following three specific aims: (i) to implement a telerehabilitation intervention in routine care after an inpatient rehabilitation stay for people insured with the Sozialversicherungsanstalt der Selbständigen (SVS), (ii) to evaluate the impact of telerehabilitation on the consolidation of goals achieved during the inpatient stay in everyday life, and (iii) to evaluate whether independence in everyday life can be increased by implementing telerehabilitation at home compared to standard care.

Our hypothesis is that the tele-reha intervention, including ongoing therapist support, will improve independence in daily living (defined as the primary outcome of this study), as measured by the Functional Assessment Measure (FAM) (Wright, 2011), compared to a control group receiving a standard paper-based program.

2 METHOD

2.1 Study Design

A longitudinal, observer-blinded, randomised controlled trial with three arms will be conducted at the Neurological Rehabilitation Center Rosenhügel (NRZ), Vienna. The CONSORT Statement 2010 and CONSORT guidelines for non-pharmacological interventions were considered in the planning of this trial and will be used for reporting the results.

All patients admitted to the NRZ receive a Baseline Assessment (T0). Rehabilitation aims are defined based on symptoms, functional limitations and participation restrictions, and routine care is provided accordingly. At discharge, patients undergo another assessment to determine if the rehabilitation aims have been reached (Post-inpatient Evaluation [T1]). Between T0 and T1, patients participating in this study will be randomly assigned to either a tele-reha group (Intervention Group) or a control group (Control Group 1) stratified for the likelihood of a positive rehabilitation outcome (determined by the multidisciplinary team), as well as age, and sex. Participation in the tele-reha group and the control group 1 is restricted to patients with SVS insurance. Additionally, a second control group (Control Group 2) will be recruited from patients without SVS insurance who only receive standard care. Control group 2 will be matched with the tele-reha group in terms of age group, sex and the likelihood of a positive rehabilitation outcome as estimated by the multidisciplinary team.

The study concludes with a final assessment (Final Evaluation) after 36 days of therapy. SVS patients from control group 1 will be offered the opportunity to participate in an additional tele-care intervention after the study ends.

2.2 Intervention

2.2.1 Tele-Reha Group Intervention

"EvoCare" is the platform for implementing the tele-care intervention, with most of the therapeutic content, such as exercise and training videos, produced by the NRZ. In addition, therapeutic content with a focus on cognition is entered into EvoCare and made available. Interventions will be selected based on the patient's primary concern in therapy, with a maximum of two activity goals and a maximum of two treatment foci set. A detailed description of EvoCare and the teletherapy devices "EvoPads" (registered medical device), enabling access to EvoCare, are provided as supplements.

"EvoCare" is a Digital Health Platform from the provider EvoCare Telemedizin GmbH and complies with both the safety class according to IEC 62304: Class A and the Medical Devices Directive 93/42/EEC. This product was approved on 12.12.2019. Patients receive an EvoPad from EvoCare on loan and free of charge for the period of participation. The EvoPad is a "tablet" with an app and the EvoCare operating system. The patient does not need an IT structure or IT skills at home. However, patients can also choose to use EvoCare free of charge via their own terminal device (e.g. laptop, handheld, PC). The therapy plan that has already been created is displayed to the patient in EvoCare as the course of treatment on a daily basis. The patients can then access digital training programmes, videos and digital video consultations via this platform. For control purposes, the patients see themselves mirror-inverted on their tablet to be able to correctly perform the exercises shown. Individual sequences (3-5 seconds on average) are recorded. The sequential video recording serves as a control tool for the therapists to provide their patients with the best possible care. The progress of the treatment allows the therapist to better monitor how the person is responding to rehabilitation and to adjust the treatment in the EvoCare platform accordingly.

It is also possible to have digital video consultations with therapists or doctors directly through EvoCare. Messages can also be sent to the staff involved.

Patients will train independently using this platform and will be supervised by their therapists and doctors in the following ways:

1) Ongoing control of the therapy provided

The supervising therapist conducts ongoing control of the therapy provided. The following methods are used to ensure ongoing control:

- Quantitative check: Every exercise or training carried out must be confirmed by the therapist in EvoCare.
- Qualitative check: Short video sequences of exercises are viewed to check for performance quality. Patients receive feedback via the chat function if necessary, and the therapist can adjust or delete exercises as needed.
- Chat support: Patients can ask questions through the chat function, which therapists will answer.
- Reaction in case of inactivity: If a patient is inactive for at least three therapy days, therapists will contact them to clarify further procedure.

2) Consultation hours

Scheduled consultations are held via video conference between patients and therapists/doctors on the therapy platform. The consultations are divided into three categories:

- Consultation hour 1 - Therapy
 - Discuss the current status of the therapy
 - Adjust therapy planning if necessary (content and logistics)
 - Document therapy-related changes in the EvoCare notes field
 - Briefly document the consultation hour in Medbase
- Consultation hour 2 - Therapy
 - Discuss the current status of therapy
 - Adjust therapy planning if necessary (content and logistics)

- Document therapy-related changes in the EvoCare notes field
- Briefly document the consultation hour in Medbase
- Medical consultation
 - Discuss the course of therapy
 - Determine goal achievement
 - Document goal achievement in the EvoCare notes field
 - Create a final report in EvoCare, print it out, sign it, and file it in the electronic medical history (MedBase)
 - Briefly document the consultation in Medbase

The tele-care consists of 36 therapy days, with 3 dedicated to "consultation hours" and 33 dedicated to "therapy activities" such as exercises and training. The interdisciplinary team determines the therapy frequency in consultation with the patients, with options such as daily, every other day. Based on this predetermined schedule, the program concludes on (therapy-)day 36.

2.2.2 Control Group Interventions

Patients assigned to one of the control groups will continue with the standard care procedure, consisting of a paper-based home-exercise programme provided by the NRZ after discharge from the rehabilitation centre. This intervention is a programme of exercises for the basic motor skills of mobility, sensitivity, strength, endurance, balance and coordination. The supervising therapists select the content during the inpatient treatment and relate it to the patient's structural and activity-related limitations. The patients are given this paper-based programme at the end of their stay and then perform the exercises independently at home without further support.

2.3 Sample Size

We estimated that group sizes of 80 in the tele-reha and the two control groups, respectively, will be needed to achieve 80% power to detect a mean difference of a score of 1 (we used a similar study which showed groups means of 74.8 and 61.9 on the FAM, (Turner-Stokes et al., 2022)) with an estimated SD of 27.5 between the null hypothesis that there would be no difference between the three groups and the alternative hypothesis that the outcome in the

tele-reha group would be different from the two control groups using an ANOVA a significance level of 0.025 (0.05/2). To adjust for approximately 15% dropouts, we suggest recruiting 95 patients per group (n=285 in total).

Sample Size Calculator

Home

Two-sample t-Test

Paired t-Test

Analysis of variance

Wilcoxon Test

Single proportion

Chi-squared Test

Fisher's exact Test

McNemar's Test

Logrank Test

Correlation Test

Sample size calculator
Version 1.060
Contact:
robin.ristl@univie.ac.at

Sample size for one-way analysis of variance

Input and calculation

Mean 1

Mean 2

Mean 3

Standard deviation

Alpha / 2 =

Power

The required sample size per group is 80.

Options

Calculate

Sample size

Power (output decimal places:)

Specific options

Advanced

Unequal sample sizes

Account for drop-outs

Bonferroni correction

2.4 Participants

Patients from the NRZ will be included in the study if they are:

- aged 18 years or older,
- experiencing problems with motor function, sensory function, cognition, swallowing or speech production (regardless of their diagnosis),
- being insured with SVS,
- agreeing to telerehabilitation after discharge,
- having sufficient motor and cognitive abilities to operate a smartphone, tablet or PC, or being sufficiently supported by caregivers, and
- being able to independently perform the targeted tasks assigned to them.

People will be excluded if they have:

- pronounced impairments in awareness, memory, attention, spatial performance, executive performance, apraxia, speech, and visual perception that do not allow a safe study participation according to the treating physicians or therapists.

In addition to the SVS patients, people insured with other health insurance companies and fulfilling the same inclusion and exclusion criteria will be included, forming a second control group matched to the SVS control group. This study takes place within the framework of a pilot project of the SVS, which is why primarily SVS patients are included. However, in order to determine whether the promised telecare for control group 1 yet alone might have an impact on adherence or other secondary outcomes, we planned a second control group (control group 2) consisting of people with other insurance carriers who will only receive the standard paper-based care.

Women of childbearing age participating in the study must take a pregnancy test before starting the study and a monthly pregnancy test during the study.

2.5 Randomisation

Once individuals are found eligible and agree to participate in the study, the participants will be assigned randomly to either the intervention or control groups (receiving standard care). To ensure a balanced assignment, the randomisation process will be stratified based on age, sex, and the anticipated likelihood of a positive rehabilitation outcome.

The likelihood of a positive rehabilitation outcome is assessed by the experts comprising the multidisciplinary treatment team. Each professional group within the team assesses the expected changes in the individual's condition following rehabilitation, taking into account the underlying condition and its severity as determined by a comprehensive assessment. The following categories are used to differentiate the likelihood of a positive rehabilitation outcome

- Significant improvement expected (2)
- Slight improvement expected (1)
- No change expected (0)

- Minor deterioration expected (-1)
- Significant deterioration expected (-2)

The randomisation will be conducted by the study team at the Medical University of Vienna, using the Randomiser System (<https://www.meduniwien.ac.at/web/mitarbeiterinnen/it-hilfe-support/it4science/plattformen/randomizer/>), occurring between T0 and T1. To facilitate stratification, the necessary variables (patient-id, age, sex, and the likelihood of positive rehabilitation outcome) will be transferred in a pseudonymised manner from the NRZ to the Medical University of Vienna. Once the randomisation is complete, patients will be informed of their group allocation through sealed envelopes.

2.6 Blinding of assessors

To minimise observer bias, the assessors will be blinded and will have no knowledge of the group allocation. The assessors will only be involved at the assessment time points, but at no other stage of this study.

2.7 Assessment

The assessments will take place in three phases. Immediately after the start of the inpatient rehabilitation (Baseline Assessment), at the end of the inpatient treatment (Post-inpatient Evaluation) and at the end of the study (Final Evaluation). All three groups, intervention and control groups, will be assessed with the same measures. The intervention group will be asked to complete additional questions (regarding the usability of EvoCare) at the Final Evaluation.

Baseline Assessment

Assessment of demographic data and patient-reported outcomes:

- Quality of Life (Numeric Rating Scale)
- Pain level at the moment (Numeric Rating Scale)
- Pain level on average in the last weeks (Numeric Rating Scale)
- Health Status (Numeric Rating Scale)
- Functional Assessment Measure (FAM) (Wright, 2011)
- Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CESD) (Eaton et al., 2004)

Post-inpatient Evaluation

In addition to the same patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) collected during the Baseline Assessment, goal achievement and satisfaction with patients' stay at the rehabilitation centre will be assessed.

Final Evaluation

At the end of the study, the participants will complete the already used PROMs, a survey specific to the telerehabilitation care they received, and satisfaction with the standard care, respectively. At this point, caregivers will also be asked to fill out a questionnaire to gather information on their experiences with tele-care or standard care.

Table 1 Overview of all variables collected or to be calculated

	Variable	Categories/Units	Type	Assessment
Stratification Variables	Age	years	metric	T0
	Biological sex	female/male	nominal	T0
	Likelihood of positive rehabilitation outcome	Likert Scale from 2 to -2	ordinal	T0
	Functional Assessment Measure	18-126 (higher score indicating better functioning)	metric	T0, T1, T2
Primary Outcome	Quality of Life	NRS 0-100 (higher score indicating better quality of life)	ordinal	T0, T1, T2
	Pain level at the moment	NRS 0-100 (higher score indicating more symptomatology)	ordinal	T0, T1, T2
	Pain level on average in the last weeks	NRS 0-100 (higher score indicating more symptomatology)	ordinal	T0, T1, T2
	Health Status	NRS 0-100 (higher score indicating better health status)	ordinal	T0, T1, T2
	Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CESD)	0-60 (higher score indicating more symptomatology)	metric	T0, T1, T2
Secondary Outcomes	ZUF 8 Patient satisfaction	1-4 (score varies according to questions)	ordinal	T1, T2
	Goal achievement scale	1-5 (higher score indicating worse goal achievement)	ordinal	T1, T2
	Experience with tele-care	1-4 (score varies according to questions)	ordinal	T2
	Experience with standard care	1-4 (score varies according to questions)	ordinal	T2

NRS – numeric rating scale

2.8 Quantitative Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics will be used to describe the study sample in detail, including calculating absolute frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and visualising results with bar charts. We will provide information on mean, standard deviation, median, minimum and maximum values for metric variables and use box plots and histograms to visualise the data. We will assess data distribution by examining the histograms and using appropriate tests, such as the Shapiro Test. This will be done for all primary and secondary outcomes.

We will compare baseline characteristics of the control (2 groups) and intervention (1 group) groups using appropriate statistical tests such as ANOVA, Kruskal-Wallis tests, or chi-square tests, depending on the nature and distribution of the data. The findings of these tests will be presented in a tabular format. We will first test the primary outcome “Functional Assessment Measure (FAM)” at T2 in an intention-to-treat manner with the last-observations carried forward in case of drop outs using ANOVA. In case of a significant result, we will perform posthoc tests to determine between which groups the significant differences occurred. In addition, we will run subgroup analyses to explore whether the intervention effect varies by different participant characteristics, such as sex and the likelihood of a positive rehabilitation outcome. For all secondary outcomes, with the exception of the CESD, we will calculate Kruskal-Wallis tests at T2 to compare the secondary outcomes between the three treatment groups, combined with post-hoc tests in case of significant results. Similar to the primary outcomes, we will perform subgroup analyses. CESD scores will be assessed using ANOVA if the preconditions are met. Bonferroni-Holm correction will be applied for multiple testing of the secondary outcomes. The project steering committee will determine the hierarchy for testing the secondary outcomes before the project starts. We will perform an intention-to-treat analysis with the last-observation carried forward method in case of drop outs.

We will document reasons for dropouts and discuss summary statistics with the project steering committee. Likewise, all adverse events will be documented, reported, and continuously monitored by the project steering committee. We will perform sensitivity analyses to test the robustness of our results. This will involve excluding participants with certain characteristics, such as comorbidities, different sex, educational status, age groups, and patients with and without missing data and then re-running the analysis to see if the results change significantly. We will use various methods to address missing data, including complete case analysis, listwise deletion, and different imputation methods. We will use R (www.r-project.org) for statistical analyses.

2.9 Ethical Considerations

The study will be conducted following the ICH-Good Clinical Practice and the Declaration of Helsinki ethical principles, in addition to all the applicable local regulations in Austria. Informed consent will be obtained for all participants, and their confidentiality and privacy will be maintained. The participants will receive full information about the study and will be informed that if they agree to participate, they can withdraw from the study at any time without giving any reason. Participants will have the right to access their data at any time upon request. The NRZ will provide tablets for telecare interventions. Accordingly, no conflict of interest or commercial benefit will be encountered. For data extraction and analyses, all data will be pseudoanonymised in that they will be separated from personal data such as names and birth data.

2.10 Data Security

A detailed description of EvoCare and the teletherapy devices "EvoPads" (registered medical device), enabling access to EvoCare, including information on data security, are provided as supplementals.

2.11 Adverse events/safety reports

Ensuring the safety of study participants is of paramount importance in this study. To achieve this, we will inform all participants that they can contact the study team at any time via EvoCare or by phone. We encourage patients to report any adverse events to the medical team immediately. If training is interrupted for more than three days, patients will be contacted by the healthcare team and asked about possible adverse events. A detailed report of any serious adverse event with a high likelihood to the study intervention, including the action taken, will be submitted to the Ethics Committee.

2.12 Benefit/risk evaluation

In this randomised controlled trial, we want to compare the effectiveness of a paper-based rehabilitation programme with a digital rehabilitation programme for patients with neurological disorders. All three groups receive similar content, but with a different delivery

method. We assume that the digital rehabilitation programme has advantages in terms of accessibility and continuity of support from healthcare professionals for patients. However, as the content is individually adapted to the needs of the patients in both cases, we do not expect any additional risks associated with participation in the digital rehabilitation programme compared to the paper-based programme.

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